
26. Polar motion

THE EARTH'S ROTATION AXIS is not perpendicular to the plane of the planetary orbits, but inclined to it by about $23^{\circ}.5$. Neither does it remain fixed in space, but instead moves as a result of various external and internal forces. The overall spin axis motion is conventionally decomposed, according to their periods, into three components: precession, nutation, and polar motion.

Precession and nutation are caused by the gravitational forces of the Sun and Moon, and even other bodies in the solar system, on the Earth's equatorial bulge. This causes the spin axis to precess, tracing out a circle with a period of about 25 700 years. Hipparchus discovered precession around 130 BC, by comparing his observations to those of the earlier Babylonians.

Nutation describes the smaller oscillations of the rotation axis, which are dominated by the 5° tilt of the Moon's orbit to the ecliptic plane. It has a period of 18.6 years and an amplitude of 17 arcsec, and was discovered by James Bradley in 1728.

More irregular movements of the Earth's spin axis (and its poles) are termed 'polar motion'. These short-term effects were predicted by Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler in 1765. Using a rigid model of the Earth, he predicted a 10-month oscillation period.

Observational proof of these predictions was obtained in the mid-1880s, when American Seth Carlo Chandler discovered that the dominant term has a 14-month period, and an amplitude of 0.3 arcsec. The difference between Euler's predicted period and the actual 'Chandler wobble' is now known to be due to elasticity of Earth's mantle, and the mobility of the oceans.

All of these effects had to be taken into account when interpreting positional measurements made from the ground, especially when using instruments which interpreted right ascension in terms of the transit times of star images across the meridian line.

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FOLLOWING THE DISCOVERY of the short-term motion of the Earth's spin axis, an international programme was set up to monitor its detailed motion. From 1900, the International Latitude Service, established by the International Association of Geodesy, set up a network of astronomical stations.

This started with six observing sites using visual zenith telescopes, at Carloforte, Cincinnati, Gaithersburg, Mizusawa, Tschardjui and Ukiah.

Others joined from the 1930s, and from 1955, some 60–90 stations were being coordinated by the Bureau International de l'Heure (BIH). The ILS was renamed the International Polar Motion Service (IPMS) in 1962, in turn replaced by the International Earth Rotation Service (IERS) in 1988.

The International Astronomical Union (IAU) set up a 'working group' to study Earth rotation in 1978, and developed an international programme to 'monitor Earth-rotation and inter-compare the techniques' of observation and analysis (MERIT). With the inclusion of VLBI, and both satellite and lunar laser ranging, observations from about 60 ground-based instruments were subsequently coordinated by the Shanghai Observatory.

THESE OBSERVATIONS formed a somewhat inhomogeneous set, with systematics of 0.1–0.2 arcsec. But they provided the only information on the irregularities of the Earth's orientation before the advent of space techniques. Several reductions of the ILS data were undertaken in the past, including a monthly publication of the pole coordinates by the now-defunct IPMS.

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The moving Tropic of Cancer, Mexico

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SINCE THE MOVE to space with Hipparcos, the effects of the Earth's precession, nutation and polar motion ceased to be relevant for the construction of these advanced star catalogues. Separating the observing platform from the Earth freed it from the enormous complications introduced by the Earth's irregular rotation.

However, a fascinating by-product of the Hipparcos mission was that the catalogue could be used as an accurate reference system extending back in time over more than a hundred years, using the proper motion of each star to propagate their positions backwards to the epoch of the historical Earth rotation observations. Remarkably, Hipparcos provided a framework within which the historical optical observations could be interpolated to yield information on polar motion in the past.

The key point is that, with positions and proper motions accurate to 1–2 milli-arcsec, the accumulated position errors, even over 100 years, would still be at levels of only 0.1–0.2 arcsec. Observations going back to the 1900s could therefore be re-interpreted within a much more accurate reference system than was available then.

COMMISSION 19 of the International Astronomical Union, as the body responsible for monitoring the Earth's rotation, duly created a dedicated group to collect the past observations of polar motion, and to prepare for their analysis in the Hipparcos reference frame.

Their historical data set was eventually based on 4 million observations of the Earth's rotation, acquired with 47 instruments at 30 observatories between 1899–1992. The first results, reduced to a preliminary pre-release Hipparcos catalogue H37, were reported in 1997, with more complete solutions reported in 2000.

The results offer some intriguing insight into the Earth's motion, and indeed into its changing structure, over the past 100 years.

One part of this huge historical data set, extending from 1931–1962 and taken from Vondrák & Ron (2000), is shown here as a 3d representation.

Time increases along the vertical axis, and the two components of the motion of the Earth's pole are shown as the other two coordinates.

Significant and surprisingly rapid changes and modulations are immediately apparent.

Before looking at what this means for the Earth's rotation, some other effects have to be accounted for. Over the past decades, as observations and theories have improved, other physical phenomena have been recognised that affect the observations of individual observatories. And these have to be corrected before attempting to interpret the motion of the bulk Earth.

Amongst these 'corrections' are several of geophysical origin, including plate tectonic motions, and variations of the local verticals as a result of oceanic tides.

For the former, for example, detailed models allow the plate tectonic motions, at around 0.01–0.05 arcsec per century, to be listed for each observatory. These sorts of corrections are particularly important for observatories lying close to plate boundaries.

THESE HISTORICAL observations reveal some remarkable phenomena at work. The most prominent periodic terms are the 14-month period Chandler wobble. Since these are superimposed on significant annual variations, they lead to a prominent 'beat period', of about 6 years, which modulates their amplitude.

The wobble's amplitude has varied since its discovery, reaching its largest size in 1910 and fluctuating noticeably from one decade to the next. Excursions during the 1950s (seen here) were also particularly prominent.

THEORY TELLS US that the Chandler wobble should die down in a matter of decades. So it has long been realised that there must be driving forces that continually re-excite it. Many possibilities have been considered and debated, including changes in the mass distribution and angular momentum of the Earth's outer core, atmosphere, oceans, or crust.

As one example, simulations show that, from 1985 to 1996, the Chandler wobble was excited by a combination of oceanic and atmospheric processes, dominated by pressure fluctuations on the ocean floors. These, in turn, arise from oceanic circulation caused by variations in temperature, salinity, and wind. And a steady drift, of about 20 m since 1900, has been attributed to the redistribution of water mass as the Greenland ice sheet melts, and to the resulting isostatic rebound, i.e. the slow rise of land formerly burdened with ice sheets or glaciers.

Other contributions to these decadal variations arise from torques between the core and mantle caused by the uneven motions at the core–mantle boundary. Even major earthquakes can cause abrupt polar motion by altering the volume distribution of the Earth's solid mass. And geomagnetic 'jerks', rapid changes of the Earth's geomagnetic field, also appear to contribute.

WILL THE huge leap in Gaia accuracies allow further insights into the interior of our Earth (e.g. Gross 2019), or even of other planets like Mars, where similar polar motion, with an amplitude of just 10 cm, has recently been observed? I will watch with interest!

Polar motion 1931–1962 from Hipparcos